

FEATURES OF THE CONSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL STATUS OF THE INDIGENOUS PEOPLES OF UKRAINE

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Summary

The problem of the status of indigenous peoples is of global relevance for Ukraine, it is exacerbated by the fact that such peoples live on its territory, and the tragic events taking place in these territories today. Determining the constitutional and legal status of the indigenous peoples of Ukraine is connected, first, with creating a list of ethnic groups that can be recognized as indigenous peoples in Ukraine according to certain legal criteria and justifying their differences from other ethnic groups, including national minorities; secondly, with the definition of the system of collective rights of indigenous peoples as subjects of constitutional law; thirdly, with the development and adoption of relevant legislation on the status of indigenous peoples of Ukraine and, fourthly, the need to create effective mechanisms to ensure the collective rights of indigenous peoples of Ukraine, which will guarantee both the exercise of these rights and equality of rights and freedoms regardless of national character and inviolability of the territorial integrity and state sovereignty of Ukraine. Ukraine has recognized the de facto rights of the indigenous Crimean Tatar people since 1991; recognition of its de jure status took place in 2014 during the occupation of Crimea by the Russian Federation. The adoption of the Law on Indigenous Peoples was the final stage in shaping their constitutional and legal status.

Keywords: *indigenous peoples, legal status, collective rights, Crimea, Ukraine*

In the context of human rights protection, more and more attention is being paid to the development of group rights, and the development trends of indigenous peoples, which include about 300 million people from more than 70 countries, are becoming more visible [12, p.1]. The processes of determining the status of indigenous peoples after the Second World War were especially intensified. Initially, the United Nations Charter of 1945 referred only to “territories whose peoples have not yet achieved full self-government” [1]. Later, a new understanding of the term “indigenous peoples” emerged: there was a transition from a “geographical” concept of law to a “sociological” one. Further progress towards the legal regulation of the status of peoples is reflected in the “Declaration of Principles of International Law on Friendly Relations and Cooperation between States in Accordance with the Charter of the United Nations” and in UN General Assembly Resolution 2625 (XXV) of 1970 [3].

It was then that international law for the first time enshrined the idea that within one independent state, in addition to the titular ethnic group, different “pe-

oples” can coexist, each of which has the right to self-determination. According to the explanatory note of the UN Rapporteur-General, the right of indigenous peoples to self-determination is considered to be fulfilled if, through their representatives, they are genuinely involved in the governance of democracy and do not suffer any obstacles to their development or discrimination [13, p.219]. Thus, in practice, the international legal concept of indigenous peoples is represented by three main approaches developed by the UN, ILO and WB, respectively. The UN is based on the concept of Jose Martinez Cobo. However, its definition is characterized by a narrow view of the category under discussion, as it is based only on historical continuity with societies that inhabited modern indigenous territories before invasion or colonization, and does not take into account the diversity of social groups that can be classified as indigenous [10, p.210-211].

A landmark event was the adoption of the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples in 2007, according to which the fundamental rights of indigenous peoples include: equality of human rights, the right to self-determination, protection against discrimination, deportation, assimilation and the right to preserve one’s cultural identity. The Declaration also enshrines the right to autonomy or self-government in matters relating to their internal and local affairs, as well as the mechanisms and means of their financing [2]. Indigenous peoples have the right to participate in decisions concerning their rights through representatives elected by them in accordance with their own procedures (art. 18), and States consult and co-operate in good faith with them (art. 19). Indigenous peoples have the right to the lands, territories and resources they have traditionally owned, traditionally occupied or otherwise used or acquired (art. 26). Military activity on the lands or territories of indigenous peoples is not carried out, except in certain cases. Before using the lands and territories of indigenous peoples for military activities, states hold effective consultations with interested indigenous peoples through appropriate procedures and representative institutions (art. 30) [4].

Unfortunately, despite the general recognition and international legal consolidation of the collective rights of indigenous peoples, subjectivity cannot be ruled out in the positions of the states in which they live. It was clearly expressed in the debate during the consideration of the draft Convention 169. The ILO Special Committee during the discussion of the final version of Art. 1 (which deals with the meaning of “indigenous peoples”) dealt with 19 amendments received from various governments and organizations [7, p.20]. This once again shows the different perception of the phenomenon of indigenous peoples and, most importantly, their different status depending on the specifics of a particular legal system.

Determining the constitutional and legal status of the indigenous peoples of Ukraine is connected, first, with creating a list of ethnic groups that can be recognized as indigenous peoples in Ukraine according to certain legal criteria and justifying their differences from other ethnic groups, including national minorities; secondly, with the definition of the system of collective rights of indigenous peo-

ples as subjects of constitutional law; thirdly, with the development and adoption of relevant legislation on the status of indigenous peoples of Ukraine and, fourthly, the need to create effective mechanisms to ensure the collective rights of indigenous peoples of Ukraine, which will guarantee both the exercise of these rights and equality of rights and freedoms regardless of national character and inviolability of the territorial integrity and state sovereignty of Ukraine. This will contribute to the development of both interethnic relations and civil society in Ukraine as a whole.

The most common view among experts is that the indigenous peoples of Ukraine should include the Crimean Tatar (according to the All-Ukrainian census of 2001 - about 250 thousand people), Karaite (according to the All-Ukrainian census of 2001 - in Ukraine lived 1196 Karaites) and Krymchaks (according to the All-Ukrainian census of 2001 - 406 Krymchaks lived in Ukraine) [11, p.37].

Other ethnic groups mentioned in Ukraine's constitutional and legal doctrine on the issue of indigenous peoples include the Gagauz and the Urums. It is noted that although these ethnic groups have a cultural and linguistic identity that distinguishes them from the titular nation, some of their features do not allow to recognize them as indigenous peoples of Ukraine. Urums as an ethnic group that originated in Crimea from people of different nationalities (primarily Crimean Greeks) and was resettled in the eighteenth century in the Azov region, are aware of themselves as part of the Greek diaspora of Ukraine and maintain cultural and socio-political contacts with Greece, do not consider themselves a separate ethnic group and indigenous people of Ukraine [8, p.10]. The Gagauz are an ethnic group that originated and formed on the Balkan Peninsula and in modern Romania. Gagauz moved to the territory of Moldova and the south of Odessa region of Ukraine together with other ethnic groups (Bulgarians, Russians) in the XIX century. Most Gagauz live in Moldova, where their autonomous territorial entity, Gagauz-Eri, now exists. The Ukrainian Gagauz diaspora, therefore, is not of autochthonous origin and connects the issues of political and legal development of its own ethnic group primarily with the existence of the Gagauz-Eri, which can be considered a national entity of this ethnic group [8, p.10]. Gagauz and Urums cannot be recognized as indigenous peoples of Ukraine in its modern borders and in the current ethno-legal situation in the country. Ethnic groups that have their own national state formations (Russians, Belarusians, Jews, Poles, Romanians, etc.) cannot be considered indigenous peoples of Ukraine and should be considered national minorities, even if Ukraine is indigenous to a relatively small part of this ethnic group. Certain ethnographic groups of the Ukrainian nation (for example, Hutsuls) and national minorities (for example, Crimean Armenians) cannot be considered indigenous peoples of Ukraine, as they do not have the characteristics of a separate ethnic group and are not a separate nationality. Ethnic groups that do not have their own nation-state and make up only a part of the global diaspora in Ukraine and have not been formed as such cannot be recognized as indigenous peoples of Ukraine on the territory of Ukraine (for example, Roma) [8, p.10].

The problem of the status of indigenous peoples is of global relevance for Ukraine, it is exacerbated by the fact that such peoples live on its territory, and the tragic events taking place in these territories today. Our country can accept only the general legal doctrine of international law used in the discussion of the problem of indigenous peoples, and critically borrow certain features of the status of indigenous peoples under the constitutional law of individual countries. The status of Ukraine's indigenous peoples should be determined by adopting its own legislation, not by receiving international legal experience. The peculiarities of the status of the indigenous peoples of Ukraine should be enshrined in the provision of these ethnic groups with certain characteristic collective rights, which are proposed to be called ethnic; the establishment of special individual rights for indigenous peoples, except in cases of preventing the disappearance of a few Crimean peoples and the consequences of deportation, should be considered inappropriate. Collective (ethnic) rights of indigenous peoples and national minorities of Ukraine should not be fundamentally different in nature and scope. This difference must be due to purely objective factors, including the non-state nature of indigenous peoples, the threat of extinction of a few peoples, and so on. These two constitutional and legal institutions can be considered as constituent elements of a more general category of ethnic minorities.

The settlement of the status of indigenous peoples of Ukraine began in 1996 after the adoption of the Constitution of Ukraine, in three articles of which there is a clear mention of the concept of "indigenous peoples". According to Art. 11 of the Constitution of Ukraine, the state promotes the development of ethnic, cultural, linguistic and religious identity of all indigenous peoples of Ukraine; under its paragraph 3 of Art. 92 rights of indigenous peoples are determined exclusively by the laws of Ukraine; in paragraph 3 of Art. 119 of the Constitution indicates that local state administrations in the relevant territory ensure the implementation of programs of their national and cultural development in places of compact residence of indigenous peoples.

In the autumn of 1996, a bill was prepared to grant special status to the indigenous peoples of Ukraine - the Crimean Tatars, Karaites and Krymchaks. However, for almost 25 years, no version of the bill has been discussed in parliament or voted on for one reason or another, mostly politically manipulative. On 22 May 2014, the penultimate day of the 13th session of the Permanent Forum, the Ukrainian delegation made an official statement on behalf of the Government of Ukraine. In this statement, Ukraine asked to be considered a state that officially supported the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples [12, p.1]. It is worth noting the participation of representatives of certain ethnic groups in Ukraine, in particular - the Crimean Tatars, in international legal forums on indigenous issues since 1994. Recognition by the international community of the rights of these ethnic groups of Ukraine to participate in solving the problem of indigenous peoples of the world cannot be considered recognition of the relevant status of these ethnic groups as

de jure indigenous peoples, but it can, with some caveats, be seen as their de facto perception by indigenous peoples.

On March 20, 2014, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine adopted Resolution №1140-VII “On the Statement of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine on Guarantees of the Rights of the Crimean Tatar People within the Ukrainian State” [6]. In the Statement, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine guaranteed, inter alia, the preservation and development of the ethnic, cultural, linguistic and religious identity of the Crimean Tatar people as an indigenous people and all national minorities of Ukraine and stated its support for the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, adopted on September 13, 2007. The Statement stated that Ukraine guarantees the preservation and development of the ethnic, cultural, linguistic and religious identity of the Crimean Tatar people as an indigenous people and provides similar guarantees to all national minorities of Ukraine. At the same time, Ukraine guaranteed the protection and realization of the inalienable right to self-determination of the Crimean Tatar people as part of a sovereign and independent Ukrainian State. At the same time, Ukraine recognized the Mejlis of the Crimean Tatar people, the executive body of the Kurultay of the Crimean Tatar people and the Kurultay as the highest representative body of the said people. In paragraph 4 of the Statement, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine announced its support for the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. The Verkhovna Rada instructed the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine to urgently submit draft laws and other normative legal acts of Ukraine that define and consolidate the status of the Crimean Tatar people as the indigenous people of Ukraine. Relevant projects were to be developed in consultation with the Crimean Tatar People’s Mejlis, in close cooperation with the UN, the OSCE, and the Council of Europe in accordance with international law and human rights standards, indigenous peoples and national minorities. The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine also instructed the Cabinet of Ministers to develop practical mechanisms for cooperation between the executive authorities of Ukraine and the Mejlis of the Crimean Tatar people.

That is why the Declaration of March 20, 2014 is historical in nature, and its implementation by Ukraine in the international arena took place during the regular annual session of the UN Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues in May 2014. During the forum, the Permanent Mission of Ukraine to the United Nations organized an event to highlight the problems of the Crimean Tatar people in Crimea. On May 23, 2014, a representative of the Mission made an official statement at the Forum in support of UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples of the United Nations by Ukraine [9, p.12].

The final stage in regulating the constitutional and legal status of indigenous peoples was the adoption by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine on July 21, 2021 of the Law of Ukraine “On Indigenous Peoples of Ukraine”. According to Article 1 of this law, the indigenous people of Ukraine - an indigenous ethnic community formed on the territory of Ukraine, is a carrier of original language and culture, has traditional,

social, cultural or representative bodies, is self-aware as the indigenous people of Ukraine, is an ethnic minority in its population and does not have its own state formation outside Ukraine. The indigenous peoples of Ukraine formed on the territory of the Crimean Peninsula are the Crimean Tatars, Karaites, and Krymchaks.

Indigenous peoples of Ukraine have received the right to self-determination within Ukraine, establish their political status within the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, freely carry out their economic, social and cultural development. Indigenous peoples of Ukraine, exercising their right to self-determination, have the right to self-government in matters relating to their internal affairs, including ways to establish their representative bodies, which are formed and operate within the Constitution and laws of Ukraine. Indigenous peoples of Ukraine have the right to preserve and strengthen their special political, legal, social and cultural institutions, while maintaining their participation in economic, social and cultural life. The state promotes the representation of the indigenous peoples of Ukraine in the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, the Verkhovna Rada of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and local self-government bodies of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol. The state has undertaken to protect the indigenous peoples of Ukraine from acts of genocide or any other act of collective coercion or violence [5, art.2].

Indigenous peoples of Ukraine and their representatives have the right collectively and individually to the full enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms as defined in the Charter of the United Nations, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples and international treaties. consent to be bound by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, as well as provided for in the Constitution and laws of Ukraine. Indigenous peoples of Ukraine have the right to equal legal protection. Any discrimination against the indigenous peoples of Ukraine in the exercise of their rights is prohibited. The state implements measures to strengthen the support of indigenous peoples of Ukraine - temporary measures taken by the state to overcome negative for indigenous people's phenomena of social, legal or cultural nature through the creation of special favorable mechanisms for the rights, freedoms and needs of indigenous peoples. Indigenous peoples of Ukraine are guaranteed the right to legal protection from any actions aimed at:

- 1) deprivation of signs of ethnicity and integrity as original peoples, deprivation of cultural values;
- 2) eviction or forced relocation from places of compact residence in any form;
- 3) forced assimilation or forced integration in any form;
- 4) encouraging or inciting racial, ethnic or religious hatred against them [5, art.3].

Indigenous peoples of Ukraine determine their own national symbols and the procedure for their application in compliance with the laws of Ukraine.

Indigenous peoples of Ukraine have the right to revive, use, develop and pass on to future generations their history, languages, traditions, writing and literature, to restore and preserve objects of tangible and intangible cultural heritage. Denial of the ethnicity or ethnic identity of the indigenous peoples of Ukraine is prohibited.

Conclusions. The problem of indigenous peoples is based on the global question of the status of peoples as bearers of a number of collective rights. The specificity of indigenous peoples is due to the impossibility of effective realization of their own sovereignty through the formation of nation-states. The collective political, economic, social and cultural rights of indigenous peoples have been recognized by the world community through the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, which has become a document of considerable political and legal force. The legal status and factual situation of the indigenous peoples of Ukraine - the Crimean Tatars, the Crimean Karaites and the Krymchaks - is due to the tragic history of their historical homeland. Ukraine has recognized the de facto rights of the indigenous Crimean Tatar people since 1991; recognition of its de jure status took place in 2014 during the occupation of Crimea by the Russian Federation. The adoption of the Law on Indigenous Peoples was the final stage in shaping their constitutional and legal status.

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